

**FUNDRAISING SYSTEM: THE ESSENCE AND PERSPECTIVES TO
DEVELOP IT IN UZBEKISTAN
(AS AN EXAMPLE OF CROWDFUNDING)**

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to analyze the current situation of fundraising system in Uzbekistan and its importance for non-government organizations. In the article the international experience of using crowdfunding is studied and its different types are referred. As well as special offers to develop crowdfunding in the Republic are set.

Key words: fundraising, crowdfunding

1. The essence of the problematic issue

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 06.07.2018. No. PD-3899, the commercialization of scientific developments and the results of scientific and technical activities are defined as one of the priority areas for the country's innovative development.

Today, commercialization is carried out mainly at the expense of commercial banks, which is an unusual function of banks, since financing of these developments is a high-risk operation.

In order to reduce risk in Uzbekistan, measures are being taken to form a system of venture financing. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 25, 2018 No. DP-5583, which created the legal framework for the creation of venture funds. The absence of financial institutions does not allow to fully implement measures for the commercialization of developments, as well as the high-quality and timely fulfillment of the tasks set

by the country's leadership by attracting a small amount of capital from private and legal entities to share.¹

Meanwhile, in Uzbekistan there is no special regulation of crowdfunding (from the English. crowd funding, crowd - "a large number of people", funding - "financing") - a special case of crowdsourcing, or rather, the cooperation of people who voluntarily provide financial support to any project or organizations. This is a really working model, the success of which has been repeatedly demonstrated by foreign examples.), which makes it difficult to develop, since it does not allow to establish the subjects of crowdfunding as participants in civil legal relations and economic relations in order to provide them with appropriate rights and obligations.

2. How does crowdfunding work?

Crowdfunding platforms are websites that enable interaction between fundraisers and the crowd. Financial pledges can be made and collected through the crowdfunding platform. Fundraisers are usually charged a fee by crowdfunding platforms if the fundraising campaign has been successful. In return, crowdfunding platforms are expected to provide a secure and easy to use service.

Many platforms operate an all-or-nothing funding model. This means that if you reach your target you get the money and if you don't, everybody gets their money back – no hard feelings and no financial loss.

There are a number of crowdfunding types which are explained below. This guide provides unbiased advice to help you understand the three most common types of crowdfunding used by profit-making SMEs and startups: peer-to-peer, equity and rewards crowdfunding.

Main types of crowdfunding

Peer-to-peer lending - The crowd lends money to a company with the understanding that the money will be repaid with interest. It is very similar to traditional borrowing from a bank, except that you borrow from lots of investors.

¹ the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 06.07.2018. No. PD-3899, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 25, 2018 No. DP-5583

Equity crowdfunding - Sale of a stake in a business to a number of investors in return for investment. The idea is similar to how common stock is bought or sold on a stock exchange, or to a venture capital.

Rewards-based crowdfunding - Individuals donate to a project or business with expectations of receiving in return a non-financial reward, such as goods or services, at a later stage in exchange of their contribution.

Donation-based crowdfunding - Individuals donate small amounts to meet the larger funding aim of a specific charitable project while receiving no financial or material return.

Profit-sharing / revenue-sharing - Businesses can share future profits or revenues with the crowd in return for funding now.

Debt-securities crowdfunding - Individuals invest in a debt security issued by the company, such as a bond.

Hybrid models - Offer businesses the opportunity to combine elements of more than one crowdfunding type.²

3. International experience

Among CIS countries Russian Federation has a great experience on crowdfunding (existing crowdfunding platforms: StartTrack.ru, MYPIO.ru, boomstarter.ru, planeta.ru, kickstarter.ru).

- Boomstarter.ru platform: 2354 successful funded projects, 516 million rubles were attracted by projects.

² https://ec.europa.eu/growth/access-finance-smes/guide-crowdfunding/what-crowdfunding/crowdfunding-explained_en

Chart 1. Volume of funds raised through crowdfunding worldwide in 2020, by region (billion dollars)³

- Planeta.ru platform: 1.7 billion rubles were attracted by projects, 7254 projects, every third project is successful.

- Starttrack.ru platform: 2.9 billion rubles attracted by projects, 120 business projects.

Of course, Russian experience is good. However the USA and Canada still keep leading position among other countries. Below, we analyze the Volume of funds raised through crowdfunding worldwide in 2020 (Chart 1).

As we can see from the chart the volume of funding through crowdfunding was very high in the USA and Canada according to the statistics in 2020. In Europe it was approximately 3,3 times lower than the first one. Middle East showed very low result on this issue. Unfortunately, Central Asian countries had no position in this chart.

Furthermore, there are many internet crowdfunding platforms to analyze, those have better results in this sphere. Below, we take you through some of the Internet’s best crowdfunding sites.

³ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/946659/global-crowdfunding-volume-worldwide-by-region/>

Table 1. Comparing the Top Online Fundraising and Crowdfunding Platforms⁴

Site	Total raised (\$)	Supporters
Gofundme	9B	50M
Indiegogo	1,5B	10M
Kickstarter	3B	15M
Fundly	330M	NA
Justgiving	NA	22M

We can see from the Table 1 that, the platform “Gofundme” is a leader on the money it raised (9 billion dollars earned) and the number of supporters (50 million people supports the site).

Studies by foreign experts show that crowdfunding is currently developing rapidly, and its global market volume has reached 114 billion dollars. In many countries the completed legislation system works on it.

In the US, crowdfunding participants must follow the rules set out in the Jumpstart Our Business Startups (JOBS) Act and register with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC). The maximum amount of capital raised through crowdfunding is \$1,070,000 in 12 months.⁵

Swiss legislation on the regulation of financial markets is based on the principle of technological neutrality, as a result of which there is no special regulation in the country of such a form of raising funds as crowdfunding. However, depending on the business model of the crowdfunding platform, participants in the process may fall under the requirements of legislation on licensing, on attracting deposits, on attracting collective investments, on consumer credit. In addition, some crowdfunding models (in particular, crowdlending, when in exchange for invested funds the investor receives a share in the company) require participants to draw up a prospectus for securities.⁶

⁴ <https://www.crowdfunding.com/>

⁵ <https://www.sec.gov/spotlight/jobs-act.shtml>

⁶ <https://www.finma.ch/en/documentation/legal-basis/laws-and-ordinances/>

The main piece of legislation governing crowdfunding in Israel is the Securities Law. According to the requirements of the Israel Securities Authority (ISA), the operator of the crowdfunding platform must be registered with the ISA. He must also ensure that the offerings on the platform comply with disclosure requirements and that any conflicts of interest are excluded.⁷

The company can raise no more than 4 million shekels through crowdfunding in a 12-month period, the number of private investors is not limited. If an R&D company receives a report from the Israel Innovation Authority containing the approval of the business plan, then the maximum amount of funds raised is increased by 1 million shekels.

ISA protects the interests of investors not by regulating disclosure of information, but by limiting the amount that an investor can invest in a particular project. The maximum amount of investment in one project is 10,000 shekels, provided that the investor's personal income is not less than 20,000 shekels.

4. Offer

In Uzbekistan we can notice a number of sites which are registered as crowdfunding platforms: vot.uz, halfana.uz, spherra.uz. Unfortunately, they haven't worked successfully as foreign platforms. We can see some elements of crowdfunding platforms in real life. For example, one can collect funding via telegram or other social network for curing the illness of his son/ daughter, friend etc. by attaching a proper number of plastic cards. Or a person can donate with the help of mobile applications like Click, Payme and Apelsin to special social projects which are registered in their system. We cannot call officially this process as a crowdfunding. According to the information we have, It is proposed to develop a draft legal act regulating the legal basis for the creation and functioning of crowdfunding to finance projects of small businesses in the early stages of their development. This legal act should include:

- verticality of the platform owner (legal entity),

⁷ <https://www.howardkennedy.com/en/latest/blog/regulation-of-crowdfunding-in-the-uk-us-and-israel-a-comparative-review>

- determining the types (classification) of crowdfunding platforms and regulating the obligations of participants,
- cash crowdfunding - investors primarily pursue certain financial interests,
- non-monetary crowdfunding - characterized by a material form of reward and is close to the product prepayment mechanism,
- charitable crowdfunding - in which the nature of the award is spiritual.
- relationship between developer, investor and platform.
- risk minimization mechanism for all participants of crowdfunding,
- conditions for granting financing to the developer,
- conditions for the investor to exit the project,
- terms of project financing for the investor,
- conditions and requirements for the inclusion of projects in the platform, according to the crowdfunding system, in order to avoid fraud,
- determination of the state regulator of the crowdfunding system of financing.

The regulation of crowdfunding in Uzbekistan will ensure the further development of small and medium-sized businesses and the innovative sector of the economy by simplifying the mechanisms for attracting funding.

Used literature:

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